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COMPETITION, COMPETITION HISTORY, TYPES AND TASKS OF COMPETITION. INTRODUCTION TO ECONOMICS

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КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ, ИСТОРИЯ КОНКУРЕНЦИИ, ВИДЫ И ЗАДАЧИ КОНКУРЕНЦИИ. ВВЕДЕНИЕ В ЭКОНОМИКУ

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RAQOBAT, RAQOBAT TARIXI, RAQOBATNING TURLARI VA VAZIFALARI. IQTISODIYOTGA TADBIQI

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abstract

The article discusses the importance of industry in ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy and the objective need to increase the competitiveness of industries. The dynamics of the development of the industrial sector in the economy of Uzbekistan is analyzed. Scientific conclusions and proposals to improve the competitiveness of industries are presented.

аннотация

В статье рассматривается значение промышленности в обеспечении конкурентоспособности народного хозяйства и объективная необходимость повышения конкурентоспособности отраслей. Проанализирована динамика развития отраслей промышленности в экономике Узбекистана. Представлены научные выводы и

предложения по повышению конкурентоспособности отраслей.

annotatsiya

Maqolada milliy iqtisodiyot raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashda sanoatning ahamiyati va sanoat tarmoqlari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning obyektiv zaruriyati haqida so'z yuritilgan. O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida sanoat tarmog'ining rivojlanish dinamikasi tahlil qilingan. Sanoat tarmoqlari raqobatbardoshligini oshirish bo'yicha ilmiy xulosa va takliflar keltirilgan.

Keywords:

Competition, free competition, pure monapolia, monopolistic competition, oligopoly, cross-sectoral competition.

Ключевые слова:

Конкуренция, свободная конкуренция, чистая монополия, монополистическая конкуренция, олигополия, межотраслевая конкуренция.

Kalit so'zlar:

Raqobat, erkin raqobat, sof monopoliya, monopolistik raqobat, oligopoliya, tarmoqlararo raqobat.

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Introduction

Competition is the most important sign of the market economy and commodity economy as a whole, a means of its development. Understanding the economic content of competition requires that it be approached from different angles. Competition is the conflict of the economic interests of market entities, which means the struggle between them to have higher profits and more elegance. The first full-fledged theoretical provisions on the struggle of competition and its driving forces, mechanisms of antitrust management appeared only by the middle of the XVIII century. In this, representatives of classical political economy are considered A.Smith and D.Ricardo's services are large. In later periods, F.Perru, A.Marshall, Dj.Keynes, W.Leontev, Y.Schumpeter, P.Sraffa, M.Porter, F.Thanks to the work of Kotler and others, the theory of competition has developed further. As we dwell on the essence of competition, it can be divided mainly into three different approaches. Including behavioral approach, structural approach, and functional approach. A. to the behavioral approach of competition. Smith's views can be included. He attributed the competition to the struggle between market entities for more favorable conditions for the purchase and sale of goods, correct, honest, without collusion, competition. He was aware of price changes as the main method of competitive struggle. In doing so, he noted that the community follows strict rules of conduct in a market that is not governed by Will (discretion), has no common purposes. Hence, competition is exactly the same "invisible hand" that coordinates the activities of market participants. F.Perru explains the rivalry as a constant threatening act. A person seeks to buy more expensive and buy cheaper in his own interests. Therefore, it has to constantly clash with competition. In a structured approach, the main focus moves from the struggle of competitors to the analysis of the market structure, the prevailing conditions in it. For example, as mentioned in the works of McConnell and Bruce, competition is the presence of a large number of independent buyers and sellers in the market, the opportunity for buyers and sellers to freely enter and exit the market.

Types of competition within one branch fields in the economic literature there is a net type-these are free competition, pure monopoly, monopolistic competition, oligopoly. In the context of free competition, there will be a huge number of enterprises in the same product producing network. In a highly organized market, many vendors offer their products. Since a net monopoly network consists of one firm, it is the only producer of an existing product (service), and solitude is formed. Monopolistic competition includes both monopoly and competitive elements. In this case, dozens of manufacturers of one type of product on the network compete with each other in terms

of achieving a favorable price and volume of production. Oligopoly is the presence and domination of enterprises in the network that are not so numerous. This is the most important sign of oligopoly. Whichever goods and services market is dominated by a relatively small number of manufacturers, the same network is an oligopolistic network. An oligopolistic network can produce the same or stratified product. Competition within the networks goes between enterprises of the same network to have a more favorable production and sales environment, to obtain additional benefits. Inter-sectoral competition consists of a struggle between different sectoral enterprises to obtain the highest profit norm. Non-traditional of competition, not recognized by society, deviating from the framework of the rules of social morality, non-economic (that is, the use of physical force, coercion, damage to the reputation of opponents, etc.) the use of methods is referred to as gyro competition. Honest competition is based on the rules recognized by society in the struggle for competition, the application of economic methods, the non-application of circumstances that contradict the interests of the community in achieving its goals and interests. On the way to increasing the competitiveness of the national economy, it is known that today we live in a period when the world market structure has changed dramatically, competition in the context of globalization has increased. In such complex conditions, such important tasks as ensuring macroeconomic stability, maintaining a high growth rate of development, increasing the competitiveness of the national economy, achieving the purchasing power of national products produced, increasing the revenue of the national currency are also implemented in our republic. As you know, wrestling means defending one's own interests, overcoming an opponent and trying to win, employing various tools and techniques. Goods, on the other hand, cannot directly change their competitiveness characteristics in the process of competition, that is, they cannot fight.

In the current market economy, the following main tasks of competition can be distinguished:

- The task of organizing;
- The task of placing the resource of the clock;
- Innovation task;
- The task of adaptation;
- The task of distribution of space;
- The task of supervising the clock.

The regulatory task of competition consists in influencing supply in order to coordinate production to demand (consumption). It is with this task that the definition of supply in the economy through demand, the composition and volume of production

through individual and social needs is achieved, that is, the economy is regulated on the basis of market laws. The task of the competition to place resources creates the possibility of rational placement of production factors in the enterprises, regions and regions where they are most productive. The innovative task of competition refers to the introduction of innovation of various manifestations, which is based on the achievements of the development of Science and technology and dictates the development of the subjects of the market economy.

In Uzbekistan, privatization, the emergence of other forms of ownership at the expense of state property plays a key role in the policy of the state aimed at the formation of a competitive environment. As a result of privatization, firstly, property is put into the hands of its owners, and secondly, it creates an atmosphere of multi-axis economy and competition. The main way to create a competitive environment in Uzbekistan is to move from a state monopoly that denies competition to a market economy that is non-governmental, based on the existence of various economic forms and assumes as much free competition as possible. Here, however, the formation of competitive relations presupposes the emergence of independent producers of goods, since the main condition for competition is the presence of freehold entities that are isolated, have their own interests on the basis of property responsibility and take on an entrepreneurial threat, their communication through the market. No matter what model of economic development the countries of the world choose, the position of the national economy in the world economy is determined by its level of competitiveness. International competition is an important factor in technical progress, and under its influence, constant updating of production, management technologies will continue, the types of products produced will be updated and the quality will increase.

Conclusion

It is of great importance that specific measures are taken to implement the norms and requirements provided for by the recently adopted law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on competition. Particular attention should be paid to limiting competition in the commodity and financial markets and not allowing behavior that leads to abuse of the dominant position, as well as prohibiting unfair competition, artificial increase or decrease in prices for goods (works, services). It is important to concentrate the efforts being made to activate these works, privatize, distrust and promote competition further strengthen the public institutions that ensure the performance of the works. In Uzbekistan, an international scientific and practical seminar was held on issues of increasing competitiveness of Uzbek manufacturers in the markets of foreign and domestic products and services. According to the strategy for the development of the

Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017 - 2021, “greater attention is paid to the formation of an effective competitive environment for sectors of the economy and the gradual reduction of the monopoly on the market of products and services; in principle, to change new types of products and technologies, on this basis, to ensure the competitiveness of national.

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